

Addressing (Inadequate) Mathematics Teacher Supply and Teacher (Mis)assignment: Considering Ireland's past, present and future

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This paper frames the issue of out-of-field mathematics [OOF] teaching, highlighting the practice as a common solution to mathematics teacher shortages and a product of the organisational constraints of staffing schools. Two approaches that have sought to address OOF teaching are documented: the provision of professional development in Ireland that increases mathematics teacher supply; and a policy initiative in the US that sought to govern teacher assignment in schools. The paper concludes with a turn to the advancements in defining OOF teaching and offers some considerations, as Ireland seeks to ensure that, where possible, secondary school students are taught by competent mathematics teachers.

Keywords: Teacher supply; out-of-field teaching; mathematics education

Introduction

Teacher supply is a significant issue facing the many state, national and international bodies tasked with governing their respective teacher workforce. In Ireland, secondary school leaders are reporting significant difficulties staffing their schools due to teacher shortages (Harford & Fleming, 2023). This issue of teacher shortages is not confined to Ireland, with reports in Australia (Peace, 2023), the US (Sutcher et al., 2019), and England (Jones, 2023) documenting a substantial shortfall in the supply of suitably qualified teachers. Furthermore, although the issue of teacher shortage is currently receiving attention in the public domain, it has been an enduring educational challenge (Sutcher et al., 2019). Mathematics teacher shortages have been omnipresent and are still being experienced worldwide (Behrstock-Sherratt, 2016). For example, in Sweden, school authorities encounter acute difficulties recruiting certified mathematics teachers (Boström, 2023); while in Estonia the existing shortage of qualified mathematics teachers could be exacerbated due to an ageing workforce and low supply of potential successors (Täht et al., 2023). Ireland, too, is experiencing mathematics teacher shortages, with school leaders identifying shortfalls in the availability of certified mathematics teachers (ASTI, 2023). However, despite the shortage of qualified teachers, mathematics classrooms are required to be staffed, and so, in such cases where a certified teacher is not available, alternative arrangements must be put in place. One such arrangement is to assign a teacher to teach a subject outside their field of academic preparation, a practice termed *out-of-field* [OOF] teaching (Conant, 1963). It is this practice of teacher misassignment that is at the core of this paper. What follows then is an account of the evolving definitions of OOF teaching and the solutions implemented – a professional development programme in Ireland and a policy initiative in the US – that have sought to eradicate its existence. These solutions were chosen to be reported on in this paper given their uniqueness – the governance of OOF teaching through policy has only been implemented in the US, while the professional development programme in Ireland is novel due to the large number of graduates. This paper also documents the most recently available figures on OOF mathematics teaching in Ireland and projected teacher shortages. The paper concludes with

considerations for the future, as Ireland, like many other jurisdictions, continues to wrestle with the enduring issues of mathematics teacher shortages and OOF teaching.

OOF Mathematics Teaching in the US

For as long as mathematics teacher shortages have been an issue, OOF mathematics teaching has been the modus operandi. Reports in the US from the 1960s (e.g., Mills, 1961) highlighted that up to a third of teachers who were teaching mathematics were underqualified. Research by Robinson (1985), which set about uncovering the incidence of OOF mathematics teaching across US, found that the misassignment of teachers to mathematics classes was common practice. In 1999, drawing on national survey data, Ingersoll identified that about a third of all secondary school mathematics teachers did not have a major or minor in mathematics, mathematics education or a related discipline. More recently, Van Overschelde and Piatt (2020) found that, in Texas between the years 2011 and 2018, 24.4 percent of mathematics classes were taught by an OOF teacher, and Shah and colleagues (2019), drawing on national survey data from 2017, concluded that 58 percent of mathematics teachers were OOF. In the case of the latter, 28 percent of these OOF teachers had either a major/ minor degree or in-field certification in mathematics, but not both. The various definitions of an OOF mathematics teacher employed in these surveys highlights a further challenge, the complexity of measurement.

Measuring OOF Mathematics Teaching

Ingersoll (2002) remarks that the way in which one defines and measures OOF teaching impacts on the amount of OOF teaching one finds. For Ingersoll, measures of OOF teaching are not concerned with the quantity and quality of training, education and experience the teacher brings to the job, rather they focus on whether the teacher is *qualified* in each of the fields they are assigned to teach, once employed in a school. The nature of, and requirements for, being qualified to teach in a subject area differ across jurisdictions, and so measures vary according to the teacher quality standards held in a particular context. Teachers typically find themselves teaching more than one subject, and therefore, may be teaching both in-field and OOF as part of their employment. As a result, measures may differ regarding whether they are focused on those teaching OOF only or both in-field and OOF, and in the case of the latter, decisions are required about the amount of teaching a teacher must be doing in an OOF subject to be counted. Concomitantly, measures of OOF teaching may differ regarding focus, for example, the number of teachers teaching OOF, the number of classes being taught OOF, or the number of students being taught by OOF teachers. In Ireland, the research on OOF mathematics teaching has reported on the former – the number of mathematics teachers who are OOF –, using mathematics teacher certification, acquired in line with the criteria mandated by the governing body, The Teaching Council, as the determining factor.

OOF Mathematics Teaching in Ireland

In Ireland, research in late 2000s uncovered the scale of OOF mathematics teaching, with 48 percent of mathematics teachers surveyed uncertified to teach the subject (Ní Ríordáin & Hannigan, 2009). This research indicated that OOF teachers of mathematics were

most likely to be under the age of 35 (60%) and assigned to lower secondary school classes. In a follow-up study by Goos and colleagues (2021) it was discovered that 25 percent of mathematics teachers were OOF, and akin to the previous study, a large proportion of these teachers were teaching at lower secondary school level. More recently, research from the Teacher Supply Data Working Group [TSDWG], on behalf of the Department of Education [DoE] (2022), found that 22.6 percent of mathematics teachers (1,438 of 6,353) are OOF. The reduction in Ireland's incidence of OOF mathematics teaching since 2009 is primarily due to the introduction of a professional development programme, *The Professional Diploma in Mathematics for Teaching* [PDMT], which enables teachers to acquire mathematics teacher certification.

The Professional Diploma in Mathematics for Teaching

The PDMT provides a route for OOF teachers of mathematics to add the subject to their teacher certification. The DoE provided €7 million in funding for version one of the PDMT (2012-2020), resulting in 1,068 teachers (4 cohorts) graduating from the programme, and committed a further €1 million for version two of the programme. It is intended that three cohorts will complete the latest version, leading to 600 teachers graduating by 2025. Research on the impact of the programme for the participants has shown that upskilled teachers developed self-efficacy beliefs akin to those of in-field mathematics teachers (Goos & Guerin, 2022), documented high levels of job satisfaction and affective commitment (Ní Ríordáin et al., 2022), and indicated a greater sense of belonging as a mathematics teacher, with validation for their practice provided by their teacher certification (Quirke, 2022). However, the latter research raised concerns about the teaching practices employed by the upskilled teachers, in addition to documenting that the teachers believed their practice was unaltered by the programme. Professional development programmes, such as the PDMT, address teacher supply as the root of OOF teaching, and as shown in Ireland, have the capacity to positively impact the issue. However, despite the progress Ireland has made in alleviating OOF mathematics teaching, it is still an ongoing challenge, particularly in the context of projected teacher shortage.

Ireland's Projected Teacher Shortage

Sutcher et al. (2019) note that teacher shortage typically refers to an insufficient production of new teachers, in response to the number of student enrolments and teacher retirements. These authors argue, however, that teacher shortage is more complex, given that it is affected by numerous factors, such as teacher turnover, changes in educational programmes, pupil-teacher ratios, and the appeal of the teaching profession both generally and in specific locations. In Ireland, inadequate teacher supply is a main cause for concern, with secondary schools experiencing a surge in enrolments, expected to peak in 2024. In their technical report, the Teacher Supply Steering Group, on behalf of the DoE (2021), projected that secondary school enrolments will have increased by 30,000 from 2019 to 2024, resulting in an additional 2,612 full-time equivalent teaching posts, taking the pupil-teacher ratio to remain constant at 12.3:1. When estimated retirements and resignations are considered, the group predicts teacher demand to exceed supply by 6,141 full-time equivalent posts. These projections do not account for teachers leaving the country to teach elsewhere, which appears

to be an ever-increasing trend (O'Brien, 2023). In any case, the projections highlight the imbalance between demand and supply, further heightening the potential for OOF teaching. Teacher shortages can also vary in accordance with location (Sutcher et al. 2019), as the projections for Ireland demonstrate: Dublin is expected to experience the largest increase in secondary enrolments by 2024 (an increase of 13.3 percent), while the Mid-West region¹ is expected to experience minimal growth (2.3 percent). Additionally, subject specialisms result in teacher shortages varying across disciplinary areas, thus leading to OOF teaching at the local level even in cases where teacher supply surpasses demand (Sutcher et al. 2019). To account for these complexities associated with teacher shortage, Sutcher and colleagues (2019) generate the following definition:

teacher shortages emerge in different fields and locations when there is an imbalance between the number of teachers demanded and the number of qualified teachers willing to offer their services to fill these demanded positions. (p. 4)

Addressing OOF teaching in different fields arising from teacher shortages is challenging; however, the issue is further complicated when the occupational and administrative characteristics of staffing schools are considered. For instance, the TSDWG research highlights that 646 teachers registered to teach mathematics are not currently teaching the subject, despite being deployed in schools. This points to other factors residing outside of the realm of teacher shortage that contribute to OOF teaching. These alternative factors derived from how schools are managed and how teachers are utilised once employed are situated within the organisational and occupational perspective on OOF teaching (Ingersoll et al., 2004).

Organisational and Occupational Perspective

In contrast to the rigorous regulations surrounding teacher certification, once a teacher is employed, school management has autonomy regarding the subjects they are assigned to teach (Ingersoll et al., 2004). This teacher assignment process for school leaders is complex; decisions are mediated by industrial legislation governing working conditions, teacher seniority issues, class-size guidelines, and contractual obligations. Additionally, teacher assignment is impacted by the need to provide a broad range of subject choice despite limitations to resources, budget, and staff, while provision must also be made for future retirements and reform efforts. Thus, the assignment of teachers at the local level constrained and impacted by a myriad of factors leads to OOF teaching. In the US, the policy initiative *No Child Left Behind* [NCLB] set about governing practices at the local level as a solution to OOF teaching.

No Child Left Behind

In the US, the NCLB policy was a unique educational reform that sought to eradicate OOF teaching, mandating that all classes were taught by 'highly qualified' teachers (McConney & Price, 2009). However, the complexities of sourcing highly qualified teachers, particularly in rural areas, resulted in schools acquiring waivers to employ teachers who did not meet the specified criteria. In line with the policy, these schools informed parents that

¹ The Mid-West region refers to the counties of Clare, Tipperary, and Limerick.

their children were not being taught by a highly qualified teacher, which consequently led to the district superintendents reassuring parents that a high-quality education was still being provided (Reeves, 2003). In 2015, the NCLB policy was replaced by the *Every Student Succeeds Act* [ESSA], abolishing the requirement of a highly qualified teacher for every class. Instead, under ESSA, each state determines teacher certification requirements and the criteria for being deemed highly qualified (ASCD, 2015). The ESSA, however, appears to be exacerbating the issue of OOF teaching, with a greater number of teachers being assigned to teach OOF (Van Overschelde & Piatt, 2020).

The approach of policy initiatives, such as the NCLB, sets out to eradicate teacher misassignment at the local level through regulation, yet teacher shortages, particularly in hard-to-staff areas, lead to the impracticalities of such a solution. Alternatively, the approach of professional development bolsters the available workforce through the provision of certification. Yet, the administrative and occupational constraints make it difficult, if not impossible, to eliminate OOF teaching in schools. Thus, although both solutions made varying levels of progress in reducing OOF teaching, neither approach has completely eradicated its existence. This highlights the complexity of the issue at hand and the need to develop innovative and sustained solutions to, perhaps not eradicate the issue, but reduce and manage its prevalence on an on-going basis. This calls for re-framing OOF teaching, and Hobbs and colleagues have done significant work in this area.

Reframing OOF Teaching

Hobbs et al. (2020) explain that an agreed definition of OOF teaching is required to inform policy, practice, and research. Subsequently, these authors distinguished six criteria which focus on numerous aspects of the phenomenon and serve to identify dimensions of ‘suitable alignment’ between a teacher and the subject/s they are assigned to teach: (1) Qualification; (2) Workload; (3) Capability; (4) Identity; (5) Structures; (6) Pathways. The first three criteria are located within the cluster, *Measurable Criteria*, with *Qualification* viewing OOF teaching as the misfit between teacher allocation and teacher qualification; *Workload* examining the allocation that maximises teacher effectiveness; and *Capability* drawing attention towards teacher expertise and experience. It is the perspective of Qualification that has dominated the Irish research landscape in terms of measuring OOF teaching, but perhaps future work should investigate both Workload, the proportion of the teacher’s load that is OOF, and Capability, the degree to which an OOF teacher has engaged with professional learning and repeated practice of teaching the subject. Cluster 2, comprising *Identity and Structures*, draws attention to the self-reported criteria paramount to OOF teaching. In terms of *Identity*, teachers mediate OOF-ness in a variety of ways, spanning from high levels of personal and professional commitment to low levels of compliance. Research on teachers undertaking the PDMT programme elucidates this point, with some teachers pursuing the programme primarily for job security while others demonstrated high personal interest in the subject (Quirke, 2022). *Structures* accounts for the ways in which school contextual factors mediate OOF-ness. Research has shown that this is experienced in different ways by different teachers. In the Quirke (2022) study, one teacher was supported by her experienced colleague, whom she referred to as her “maths support worker” (p. 279), through

the sharing of resources and feedback, while another teacher refused to ask colleagues for assistance, highlighting that this may be viewed as a sign of weakness. The final cluster, *Longitudinal Criteria*, encompassing *Pathways*, addresses the mechanisms by which an OOF teacher can become in-field. These mechanisms can be subdivided into qualification upgrade – the approach offered in Ireland through the PDMT, professional development concentration – which may be a precursor to micro-credentialing, and experience – be it sustained or temporary. How the OOF teacher then experiences the pathways implicates their identity, in the sense that they may accept the subject with extended identity, accept the subject but their identity is not extended to include the subject, or the teacher may not accept the subject, reluctantly teach it, and not acknowledge it as part of their identity. And so, this extensive work of Hobbs and colleagues points towards the lack of homogeneity across OOF teachers and their experiences, indicating that a one-size fits all approach may not best cater for their variety of needs.

Discussion

The definition for OOF teaching has evolved since the work of Conant (1963), Robinson (1985), and Ingersoll (1999, 2002). Being defined as OOF must now account for how the teacher feels; how the teacher views oneself and is viewed by others; along with their academic preparation, certification, expertise, and experience. Thus, the existing measures used for researching OOF teaching based on certification alone may not be capturing the phenomenon as it is now defined. There is a need then to develop more nuanced approaches for researching OOF teaching that reflect the theoretical advances. Furthermore, OOF teaching remains an under-documented and under-researched area. The reluctance to openly discuss and research OOF teaching is unsurprising, particularly given the possibility that this may jeopardise the teaching profession. Additionally, OOF teaching serves an important role in addressing teacher shortages and the unequal distribution of teachers both geographically and with respect to their subject-specific qualifications (Hobbs et al., 2020). Therefore, discussing and reporting on OOF teaching is a sensitive issue; it requires the complexities of the issues at hand to be accounted for and the provision of respect and acknowledgement for the work of OOF teachers. Moreover, often it is the case that these OOF teachers are subjected to misassignment as part of the recourse adopted by school leaders in response to broader, system-level challenges.

In Ireland research is required on where the PDMT teachers are now, investigating if they are still teaching the subject, and if not, the reasons for this. This would inform future iterations of the PDMT and other upskilling programmes such as those in Physics and Spanish teaching that have recently been introduced. Consideration must also be given to evolving the PDMT, acknowledging that teacher shortages coupled with organisational constraints inevitably lead to some level of OOF teaching. This advancement of the PDMT may consider the contributing factors to OOF teaching in terms of being *long-term* and *short-term*. From a long-term perspective, history informs us that mathematics teacher shortages have been ever-present, and so ongoing work is required to address this issue. The PDMT is suitably designed to continue in this respect. Short-term contributory factors occur at the local level, whereby school management misassigns teachers typically for a short period of time, often, in their

view, for the betterment of the school in the long term. These decisions may, in some cases, be made due to succession planning and/or to increase subject choice for students. Short-term solutions are required for teachers who find themselves in such a position; this may not be in the form of acquiring formal certification, but it may offer some credentials that are acknowledged if subsequent study for teacher certification is pursued. There is also a need for greater awareness amongst school management of the consequences of misassigning teachers. In Texas, for instance, the tracking of student performance on courses taught by OOF teachers highlighted the detrimental effect the practice had on learning (Van Overschelde, 2022). Perhaps similar research could take place in the Irish context to inform future decisions made at the local level. Ireland has made significant progress in reducing OOF mathematics teaching; however, considering the projected increase in teacher shortages and the organisational constraints of staffing schools, Ireland must continue to be innovative and progressive dealing with the issue.

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